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MOSAIC co-creation methodology toolkit

Deliverable No. 4.2

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28/02/2023

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

Executive Summary

This document describes the MOSAIC co-creation methodology. This methodology is particularly fit for the identification of solutions by quadruple helix stakeholders, and it is to be used in Open Innovation contexts where there is need for shared ideas that can help tackle big challenges (missions) that our world is currently changing. The methodology is currently being used by two pilot cities - Gothenburg (SE) and Milan (IT), who are part of the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission.

The aim of this document is to describe the co-creation process, and for each step to provide tools which can be used by cities, or other stakeholders, who might want to use the methodology in the future. The co-creation process consists of three main phases and lasts around 10 to 12 months. In the case of MOSAIC, the entire process was driven by project partners SD and FGB, together with the local city representatives. MOSAIC provides the selected mission cities with full support with the local adaptation of the methodological approach, facilitation, coaching, and ad hoc troubleshooting.

This document is currently a work in progress, as at the time of submission the two pilot cities are entering the third stage of the process. While we already provide at this stage detailed information on the first two stages, a new version of the deliverable will be submitted during the summer 2023, including tools for Phase 3 as well as reflections on lessons learnt, and more dedicated tips for initiators of such processes in the future.

Deliverable Information

D4.2 – Title of the deliverable	
Deliverable number	4.2
Responsible partner	SD
Due date of deliverable	28/02/2023
Actual submission date	28/02/2023
Version	Version 1
Authors	Marzia Mazzonetto, Maria Zolotonosa, Carmen Fenollosa, Fabien Lambert, Angela Simone, Federica Manzoli, Anna Pellizzone, Mélanie Marcel, Mireille Matt
Reviewers	Angela Simone, Maria Zolotonosa
Work package number	4
Work package title	Open Innovation on stage through Co-creation
Work package leader	SD

Dissemination Level		
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

Nature of the Deliverable		
R	Report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
D	Demonstrator	<input type="checkbox"/>

W	Website, patent filing, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
O	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>

Partners Involved in the Deliverable

Participant No.	Name of the Organisation	Short Name	Involved
1	Stickydot srl	SD	X
2	Fondazione Giannino Bassetti	FGB	X
3	Universite Gustave Eiffel	UNI EIFFEL	X
4	SoScience	SoScience	X
			<input type="checkbox"/>
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			<input type="checkbox"/>

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Phase 1: Preparation and setting of the scene (Months 1-4)

Objectives of the phase

- To finalise the MOSAIC methodology with the city, identifying potential minor adaptations to the local context
- To select the challenge for co-creation together with city representatives – based on the priorities listed in their “Climate City Contracts”
- To get a deep understanding of the context around the chosen challenge (stakeholders to be involved, previous consultations/participatory activities if any, local context)
- To launch and promote a call for applications for Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders who are interested in getting involved in the co-creation process on the chosen challenge.

Process

1. Defining the challenge

- Online workshop with city representatives, discussing the methodology and making first steps in the challenge selection
- In-person challenge definition workshop with city representatives (including colleagues from other departments working more closely with the selected challenge, if possible)
- Characteristics/criteria for the challenge:
 - Related to the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities mission objectives and the City’s Climate City Contract
 - Challenge that concerns local QH stakeholders
 - Challenge should be framed around a desired outcome, not a potential solution (e.g. Mobility and not EV)

2. Call for applications for participants

- Preparation, publication and promotion of the call for participation for QH stakeholders (description of the challenge, who can apply, selection criteria, how to apply, timeline, fair reward requirements, etc.)
- Support the open call by actively reaching out to specific stakeholders and inviting them to get involved
- Development of the criteria for the selection of stakeholders.

3. On-the-ground support activities for inclusion

- Map and Identify stakeholders who most likely will not apply to the open call for various reasons, including but not limited to lack of time and/or resources, lack of motivation, lack of trust in potential impacts, etc.
- Contact and arrange meetings (in person, by phone or video-call) with such stakeholders to assess their views on the chosen challenges, as well as reasons for not getting involved in the process.

- Find solutions or options that will allow their participation and inputs

4. Selection process

Once the call is closed, make the selection of participants (30-50 people). The Selection Committee is composed of city representatives + MOSAIC, it will make the selection based on defined criteria and ensure a balanced representation of stakeholder groups and areas of expertise.

What is expected from the process initiator

- To participate in the requested workshops and mobilise other departments/stakeholders if and when needed, based on the chosen challenge.
- To take responsibility and ownership of the selected challenge.
- To define a clear commitment towards the uptake of co-creation outcomes which can be transparently communicated to participants from the start.
- To be in charge of the active promotion of the call for applications
- To have a dedicated member of staff for weekly contact/Interactions with the MOSAIC team (applicable to all phases)
- To ensure the call for action meets the city internal processes and requirements (procurement etc...)

TOOLS

1. Choosing your co-creation challenge

Introduction

This tool describes the process leading to the identification and definition of a challenge which can be addressed through co-innovation. The challenge definition should always go hands in hands with a process involving all concerned stakeholders, also called “co-design” phase. Through co-design activities such as consultations, agenda-setting, climate assemblies and more, Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders are engaged in a process that leads to the identification of shared challenges.

For example: a city is in the process of preparing its strategic plan to achieve climate neutrality by 2030. Citizens, civil society organizations, researchers, innovators and companies are involved in a wide consultation process through various approaches. An online consultation is made available for all citizens to express their ideas. Workshops are organised involving each stakeholder group separately, around the main question of “Let’s imagine our city in 2030”. Stakeholders are asked to express first what they think should change and how they envisage their city in 2030, then they are led to express ideas and priorities which could make it happen. Priorities and ideas emerging from the consultative processes are matched with existing strategic policy agendas, and potentially further discussed with stakeholders with the aim of identifying common ground. Shared strategic priorities therefore emerge and are integrated in new policies and action plans.

In the specific case of MOSAIC and the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities mission, the co-design phase corresponds to the cities’ work towards the preparation of their Climate City Contracts. MOSAIC pilot

cities have already done this work in the past, leading to the identification of strategic priorities for climate neutrality within their own local contexts.

Key points

Look at your Climate City Contracts through the lenses of multi-stakeholder engagement.

The first step in the challenge identification is therefore to carefully look at existing Climate City Contracts (or to strategic plans which will be used as a basis for the Mission CCC) and establish which are the challenges that were particularly attracting stakeholders' attention and motivation during the co-design phase. Alternatively, you can identify them based on your own experience of your local context. Attracting stakeholders' attention does not necessarily mean choosing a challenge on which everyone agrees.

For example, citizens might be advocating for a city with less cars and more green spaces, innovators, companies and universities might be pushing towards electric cars and related infrastructure and technology advancements, while local businesses and associations, although aware of the importance of reducing pollution from cars, are also concerned about the impact on their activities and revenues. This is a typical broad challenge which could be interesting for you to focus on and to identify a specific mission project within it for your co-innovation process.

Large or small-scale challenges?

Co-innovation allows you to address a large variety of challenges, even broad ones, although there are several elements you should consider when picking one. The first and most obvious one is your availability in terms of efforts, support and budget you can dedicate to the process you want to implement. Large-scale co-creation processes can be time consuming and a bit costly - they require more efforts than consultations and other co-design activities. The infrastructure required should also be considered. A less obvious aspect regards commitment: as a city representative, if you initiate a co-innovation process, you should reflect upon what it is concretely possible for you to do to support the uptake of what will emerge from it. The choice of your challenge will therefore necessarily require a negotiation process between your city's political agenda and stakeholders' identified priorities.

For example, co-developing solutions towards better public transport options that will motivate more and more people to change their commuting habits is a challenge that concerns the entire city. But different neighbours or specific areas of your cities might face different challenges. You can therefore either set up a city-wide co-innovation process while still ensuring that local working groups address specific contexts, having major stakeholders involved (such as private companies managing public transport systems or producers of public transport means). Or you might want to start by focusing on specific target groups or areas of your city, as test beds for further developments, while still having large key players involved. It might also be easier to convince them to get involved in a smaller case co-innovation process to start with.

Your challenge formulation matters

When defining your challenge, it is key to a co-innovation process to provide a formulation of the problem that allows all participants (and therefore all stakeholders groups) to feel like there is something in it that concerns them and on which they can have a say, and therefore not to miss the views of certain groups. If you are addressing a broad challenge like air pollution and you want to focus on a specific source of contamination, you should make sure that relevant stakeholder groups will not refuse or be reluctant to get involved in the process just because they feel like it's something too far away from them.

For example, in the case certain specific types of industries (i.e., manufacturing, power plants, etc.) or a specific sector (i.e., tourism) are a big source of pollution in your city, citizens or other types of local actors might feel discouraged to get engaged and provide their contribution due to frustration towards whether anything will ever really change. Framing the challenge in a way that highlights the potential positive impacts for all the co-innovation and its implementation is key to engaging stakeholders. We recommend to frame challenges around the social or environmental outcomes instead of framing it around technical solutions or options.

Keep in mind your final aim

In a co-innovation process, your desired outputs are tangible outcomes, such as technologies, services or new organisational structures.

Overall, your challenge should:

- Be broad enough and always have a clear link to your Climate City Contracts. It should not be a merely technical challenge (for example, 3D printing is not an eligible topic)
- Besides addressing challenges recognised by the scientific community and supported by scientific data, the challenge should also have a strong link with societal needs that you have identified through your co-design phase.
- Ideally, the challenge should foster solutions that respond to technical, economic, social and environmental issues.

Guiding questions

- Within your CCC, which are the priorities / challenges which resonate the most to key stakeholders in your city?
- Do you know your stakeholders' views on your chosen challenge? If so, can you list some of them?
- Is your challenge addressing societal needs?
- How likely will you be able to mobilise 4H stakeholders in a co-creation process around your chosen challenge?
- Is your challenge range (from very small/localised to very broad and lengthy) adapted to your availability in terms of efforts and budget?
- As a public authority, what can you “commit to” regarding your chosen challenge? If not a formal commitment, what actions do you think you will be able to take / support in case satisfying ideas emerge from the co-creation process?
- What do you think could emerge from a co-creation process around your chosen challenge?

2. The Challenge definition workshops

These workshops can be held online and last around 2 hours each. We suggest two workshops, but there can be more sessions if needed. We suggest to regularly plan energizers or similar activities to keep participants involved. In case the participants are not familiar yet with the methodology and the process, we suggest introducing those before working on the challenge definition.

Suggested activities:

- Presentation of the methodology (Overall process) - focus on what is expected by the initiator(s) and participants, and stimulate reflections on challenges that might be faced.
- Presentation of the challenge rationale.
- Time for comments and QA
- Familiarising with the current context. For example, invite participants to share experiences, and citizen engagement activities, that they think can be relevant to inform or influence the chosen challenge.
- Individually brainstorm on a strategic priority you want to tackle with the co-creation.
- Share with others how your idea for a strategic challenge fits with the “challenge rationale”, and why you think this challenge can be addressed with the MOSAIC co-creation approach.
- Prioritise propositions to identify the preferred one.
- Check the chosen challenge against the rationale.
- Once your challenge is chosen, focus on agreeing on common goals for the co-creation process. For this, you can use an ideal scenario/visioning exercise, which will also help you identify what goals you want to have for your co-creation process.
- Use a problem definition canvas to formulate and re-frame the challenge.
- Define your commitment (especially in terms of up-take of co-creation results).
- Decide who should be involved in this process, who is key to solving the challenge?

<p>What is the key social problem/need you are addressing and why is it important?</p> <p><i>Explain the reasons why the problem/need is important.</i></p>	<p>What social/cultural factors shape this problem?</p> <p><i>Sociocultural factors are customs, lifestyles and values that characterise a community. You could think about esthetics, education, language, law, politics, religion, technology, material culture, values and attitudes.</i></p>	<p>Who is it a problem important/relevant for?</p>	<p>What evidence do you have that this is a significant problem?</p> <p><i>You might also want to think about the stakeholders and their opinion about the problem.</i></p>	<p>Can you think of the problem in a different way? Can you reframe it?</p>
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You are now ready to start your stakeholder mapping in relation to the challenge.

3. Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder mapping is a tool used to identify and analyze their stakeholders. In this process, stakeholders are individuals or groups that have an interest in or are affected by the chosen challenge. In the MOSAIC co-creation process we involve stakeholders from the « quadruple helix », meaning representatives from the public sector, academia, the private sector and civil society.

The purpose of stakeholder mapping is to think about all possible type of stakeholders that have a stake in the chosen challenge, even indirectly. The stakeholder mapping can then be used to identify participants to invite to the Gathering and following activities.

Stakeholder mapping typically involves creating a visual representation of the stakeholders and their relationships to the challenge. This can be done using a variety of tools, such as a matrix or a spider diagram. The mapping process should be iterative and eventually involve feedback from stakeholders to ensure that no relevant participants are left behind.

Below is an example of the stakeholder mapping conducted on Mural (online) with representatives of the city of Gothenburg, around the challenge of making mobility in the city more sustainable.

3 Stakeholder mapping - 23 November 2022

The objective of this workshop is to identify specific organisations and individuals that we can invite to the co-creation process. Please think of the four QH stakeholder groups according to how much or little they are related to the challenge.

Phase 2: Forming teams and defining collaborative projects (Months 5-6)

Objectives of the phase

- To bring together and onboard city's QH stakeholders
- To select co-creation teams that will address the challenge
- To support them in working together toward the objective
- To facilitate networking and getting-to-know each other opportunities
- To support them in working together toward the objective

Process

1. The Gathering

- The first big gathering of all selected participants and the organising team is the moment of formation of co-creation teams and the kick-off of the co-creation work.
- The objectives of The Gathering are two-fold: (i) for participants to get to know each other (and better understand each other's expertise) and form co-creation teams, (ii) To further assess stakeholders' views on the challenge and help them find common ground
- Activities taking place during The Gathering: i.e. participatory sessions (starting by working in separate stakeholder groups), mini-ideation sessions, speed-dating, social moments

2. Launch of group work – idea identification

- All formed teams go through a facilitated process to kick-off their work on the selection and identification of their idea
- The groups then work on their own milestones and deliver a draft idea (vision) within a short timeframe (i.e a month) Based on that vision the Selection Committee selects 3 teams to be actively supported in the co-creation process

What is expected from the process initiator

- Logistical support in the organisation of The Gathering
- Clear commitment and ownership of the programme (e.g. support offered to the most interesting ideas or other types of commitment)
- (ideally) The city should ideally provide a place for the participants to meet throughout the whole process and access to city resources that might be needed.
- MOSAIC commits to supporting 3 teams in the co-creation process; the city needs to decide whether they want to do something with extra-groups

TOOLS

1. The Gathering structure

Objectives of the Gathering

- To bring together for the first time all selected participants and the organising team
- For participants, to get to know each other and better understand each other's expertise, experiences, needs and ideas
- To further assess stakeholders' views on the challenge and facilitate activities that will lead them to identify common ground and shared ideas
- To form 3 groups (co-creation teams) that will be working separately on ideas and potential solutions to address the specific challenge
- To kick-off of the co-creation work

Structure

PART 1 (duration: 3 to 4 hours)

00:00-00:20 Welcome and introduction

Quick icebreaker: the lead facilitator, without introducing herself/himself, asks the participants to say one word they associate with the topic of the challenge – words are introduced in a Sli.do by a notetaker in real time, forming a word cloud that is projected on a screen. Brief introduction about the challenge, the aims of the co-creation process and timeline and explanation of the framework (how we will work together) and code of conduct.

00:20-01:00 Contextualisation

Short pitches by external speakers aimed at providing a brief, neutral introduction on existing data, studies, geographic data, etc. regarding the challenge topic. Pitches in the case of the MOSAIC pilot cities also focused on making more explicit the links between how the co-creation process can contribute to the city priorities (e.g. its Climate City Contract).

01:00-02:00 Barriers and concerns

Exercise 1: participants are provided with an A3 hand-out and invited to draw on it following a topic specific question. Participants are then invited one by one to explain what they have been drawing to the rest of the group. This exercise is aimed at breaking the ice and getting participants to focus on the challenge topic. It is also helpful to get an understanding of their current habits around the topic.

Exercise 2: participants are asked to think about challenges / barriers / concerns they encounter, feel or perceive in relation to the topic of the co-creation. They are given a few minutes to write on post-its. The facilitator then asks them to share what they wrote, and clusters post-its on a flip chart.

02:00-02:15 Break

02:15-03:00 Visions and opportunities

Exercise 3: Participants are asked to focus on a question that makes them think about their vision of the future in relation to the challenge, and what changes are needed in order to get there. Example of a question: How will the city look like in 2030 in relation to the challenge? What will be the main observed transformations?

The facilitator explains that the co-creation project should contribute to shared desired objectives, and that these objectives can change and be revisited during the course of the programme.

Participants are invited to write their visions and expected transformations on post-its (one per post-it). The facilitator then asks them to share what they wrote, and clusters post-its on a flip chart.

03:00-03:20 Sharing of outcomes

A representative of each stakeholder group (ideally not the facilitators but a member of the group) shares main outcomes of exercise 2 (barriers and concerns) and exercise 3 (visions and opportunities).

3:20-3:30 Closing and introduction of Part 2

Part 2 (3 to 4 hours)

00:00-00:20 Welcome and recap

Welcome back and agenda of the day. Reminder of main outcomes of Part 1, highlighting potential common ground.

00:20-00:50 Getting to know each other – part 1

Activity: the off-line social network. Participants are invited to make a sketch of themselves on a piece of paper, write their name, and then stick the drawing on a big paper on a wall. Participants are then invited to split into pairs and have a few minutes to find at least one thing (possibly not work-related) that they share or have in common. They are invited to draw lines on the paper connecting their sketches in case they find something in common. The same process is repeated at least 4 or 5 times, depending on timing.

00:50-01:20 Getting to know each other – part 2

Activity: the crazy 6s. Participants are split into mixed-stakeholder groups (6 people per group). They are invited to think about crazy ideas related to the challenges. They are provided a hand-out where they are asked to very quickly draw one idea per minute (6 minutes in total for 6 ideas). Participants are then invited to share with the group their top two ideas, one by one.

01:20-01:35 Break

01:35-02:30 Forming groups

Participants are invited to write on a piece of paper an idea in relation to the challenge (i.e. solution, product, service). These should be formulated in the form of “My name is ... and my proposition is...”. The facilitator reminds participants about what already discussed so far, and previous exercises. The papers are then stuck to a white wall. Each participant is invited to briefly share their idea with the group. Not all participants have to make a proposition, the facilitator explains that it is ok not to have one.

The facilitator clusters ideas as much as possible, with the aim to try and reduce them to three groups. If not possible, the facilitators give three stickydots to each participants and asks them to vote for their three favourite propositions (or clusters of propositions). Only the three top voted propositions are used in the next steps (the other propositions are kept for potential use in the future, in case one of the top-three ones does not move forward).

Participants are invited to go stand next to the proposition out of the three that they would like the most to work on in the future. Three groups form. The facilitators invited them to look at the colour of their badges, and check whether all four colours are more or less equally represented in their group. If not, participants are invited to kindly move to their second favourite proposition, explaining that groups have to be balanced and inviting them to be collaborative and volunteer to move if needed. Working groups are therefore shaped (ideally no more than 10 participants per group).

02:30-03:20

The three groups are invited to gather and sit separately (one facilitator per group). The groups are provided with a template of points they have to work together on:

- (20 minutes) discuss together the concept of their co-creation proposition that emerged in the previous exercise, explaining that it can evolve into something different than originally stated (the facilitator makes sure all voices are heard). When agreeing on a proposition, participants are invited to think and write in the template about its expected transformations (desired goals); the barriers/challenges/concerns it addresses; the envisioned solution (in a very draft form); and a “wow sentence” about it (its starting/selling point).
- (20 minutes) groups are invited to plan how they want to work together. On the template, they fill together information on a) agreeing on at least one date to meet next; b) what are their needs in terms space, facilitation, tools, etc. c) distribution of roles and responsibilities; d) how to stay in touch (communication channels to be used).

03:20-03:30 Wrap-up and closing

2. Template for idea definition and planning further work

Idea Card

As a group you should try and agree on your initial idea. After this meeting you will get the chance to revisit the idea and even change it completely if needed. You have 20 minutes for this exercise.

<p>1. Challenge</p> <p>What challenge are you addressing?</p>	<p>2. Solution</p> <p>If the problem was solved, what would it look like?</p>
<p>3. Idea</p> <p>Describe your idea</p>	<p>4. What is the unique selling point of your idea?</p> <p>What is the “wow” effect?</p>

Planning future work

<p>What roles are important to have in your team? Who can be in charge of what?</p>
<p>What are your needs in terms of meeting spaces, tools, further support?</p>
<p>What communication channel will you use to keep in touch? Who will set it up?</p>

When will you meet next to advance the work?
How can we contact your team?

3. Observation template and evaluation form

Aims	
Aims of the observation	To collect additional information about: Stakeholder views on the challenge Differences in opinions and common ground Group dynamics
Topic	Question
Observer	Form filled in by:
Stakeholders	As far as you know : How many participants took part in the event? Which stakeholder group was the largest/the smallest? What is your general view of the group? Were any important stakeholders / participants missing? Were the participants complementary to each other? Were they mostly aligned with peers from same stakeholder group? If not, can you briefly elaborate?

<p>Atmosphere</p>	<p>Can you describe the atmosphere during the meeting in three key words? E.g good / tensions / collaborative other...</p> <p>Can you briefly elaborate?</p>
<p>Evaluative questions</p>	<p>What went well?</p> <p>Please describe a situation (e.g. what, who, what were the outcomes, why do you think it went well?):</p> <p>What can be improved? How and why?</p> <p>Please describe</p> <p>What remark or discussion comes to mind immediately?</p> <p>Please describe:</p>
<p>About the event</p>	<p>Can you describe a situation that stood out in a positive way?</p> <p>Please describe:</p>
	<p>Can you describe a situation that needs more attention next time?</p> <p>Please describe:</p>
<p>Dynamics of the engagement</p>	<p>Was there any common ground/common views/consensus that you noticed?</p> <p>Was there one or more contributions of a participant which stood out in a positive or negative way?</p> <p>Please describe:</p> <p>What was the (main) challenge the participants talked about during the event?</p>
<p>Suggestions</p>	<p>What suggestion for improvement would you – as an observer – give for the next steps?</p>

Summary	Can you provide a short summary of the event with help of a few keywords or sentences?
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4. MOSAIC Evaluation Questionnaire

Thank you for your participation in these two workshops (The Gathering). To help us analyze our practices and improve future activities, please answer these few questions.

What is the color of your badge?

Blue Red Yellow Green

On a scale of 1-10 (1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest) ...

1- How satisfied are you with what you gained (either personally, as an institution or as resulting impact) in this gathering?

2- Do you consider your time was well-spent by participating?

3- Do you feel your concerns were treated fairly compared to concerns of other participants?

4- Following The Gathering, do you think you have a better understanding of the concerns of other stakeholders (e.g. private actors, citizens, civil servants, etc.)?

- 5- Following The Gathering, did you include other type of participants' (e.g. private actors, citizens, civil servants, etc.) point of view to inform your perspective on the topic?

- 6- When you had divergent opinions, do you feel that the process helped you address these conflicts?

Phase 3: Ideation and prototyping (Months 7-12)

Objectives of the phase

- To generate ideas for solutions for the selected challenge and to make sure they are not only innovative, but also represent an added value for all those involved, and for the city overall (the common good and the mission objectives).
- To step beyond the obvious solutions and increase the innovation potential of the solution through co-innovation.
- To prototype tangible and concrete products, services or organisational structures
- To test such solutions (if time allows) by allowing users to experiment and interact with the prototype to assess the functions and scope of the product or service, providing a focused feedback loop for users

Process

1. Ideation

- Ideation uses creativity and innovation in order to develop solutions to the challenge at hand. The key activities during this phase should help us make random connections and brainstorm, to explore the problem in all directions.
- Workshops (ideally two) where teams will be invited to use creative methods to develop new solutions.
- Examples of activities that will take place during the workshops are: I.e. fast sketching exercises, reverse brainstorming activities, and *walkshops* designed to get a better understanding of the environment you are in.

2. Idea selection

- Starting from the results of the ideation workshops, this phase will help the groups narrow down solutions that offer more potential. This includes not only the potential to solve the problem but also its scaling-up capacity.
- A workshop with all stakeholders including city representatives to assess the different solutions against set criteria.

3. Prototyping

- During the prototyping phase, the teams will develop an early sample, model or release of a product created to test and be discussed by the different users and assess their features and usability. The prototyping phase will be divided into two rounds.
- Round 1: Development of lo-fi general prototypes of the solutions. Teams will be asked to prototype the solution in its entirety but the level of detail will be low. Teams will also be invited to identify what element of their prototype is the most problematic or crucial to be further developed during Round 2.
- Round 2: For this second round, teams will be asked to focus on one crucial element of the prototype that will be key in its success or failure. For this prototype, teams will be invited to be very detailed on their delivery.

What is expected from the process initiator

- To closely follow and be involved in the idea selection and prototyping process to make sure that the proposed ideas are in line with the Mission and the Climate city contract
- To be available to take over the process once MOSAIC intervention finishes
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TOOLS

Tools will be shared in the next version of the deliverable. They are currently being tested by pilot cities.

Planned update of this toolkit

This document is the first version of the toolkit, it contains carefully prepared and curated tools and materials aimed at running co-creation processes in open innovation settings. At the time of publishing this deliverable only a few tools in this toolkit have been tested in the two pilot locations - Milan and Gothenburg. The process has not been concluded yet so it is too early to make conclusions or recommendations. An updated version of the toolkit is planned to be released in September 2023. It will contain lessons learnt as well as tips and tricks from the ground. The updated version of the toolkit will be promoted at the MOSAIC final event and disseminated among MOSAIC's target groups.